

THE PROBLEM OF PRESERVING INTERTEXTUAL CONNECTIONS IN TRANSLATION

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Abstract. *This article examines the issue of preserving intertextual connections in the translation process. Intertextual units—such as quotations, allusions, irony, and other cultural-connotative elements—are particularly important in the translation of literary texts. Based on the scientific views of scholars such as Verbitskaya, Guseva, Kuzmina, and Chernyaevskaya, the article illuminates strategies for identifying intertextual elements and adequately expressing them in the target language.*

Keywords: *intertextual connection, literary translation, cultural connotation, transcreation, transformation, annotated translation, translator competence, semantic layer, poetic function*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada tarjima jarayonida intertekstual aloqalarning saqlanishi masalasi ko‘rib chiqiladi. Intertekstual birliklar — ya‘ni iqtiboslar, alluziyalar, kinoyalalar va boshqa madaniy-konnotativ elementlar — ayniqsa adabiy matnlar tarjimasida muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Maqolada Verbitskaya, Guseva, Kuzmina hamda Chernyaevskaya kabi olimlarning ilmiy qarashlari asosida intertekstual unsurlarni aniqlash va ularni adekvat tarzda maqsadli tilda ifodalash strategiyalari yoritiladi.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *intertekstual aloqa, adabiy tarjima, madaniy konnotatsiya, transkreatsiya, transformatsiya, izohlashli tarjima, tarjimon kompetensiyasi, semantik qatlam, poetik funktsiya.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматривается проблема сохранения интертекстуальных связей в процессе перевода. Интертекстуальные элементы — такие как цитаты, аллюзии, ирония и другие культурно-коннотативные единицы — играют особенно важную роль в переводе литературных текстов. В статье на основе научных взглядов таких исследователей, как Вербитская, Гусева, Кузьмина и Черняевская, освещаются стратегии выявления интертекстуальных компонентов и их адекватной передачи на языке перевода.*

Ключевые слова: *интертекстуальная связь, литературный перевод, культурная коннотация, транскреация, трансформация, перевод с пояснениями, переводческая компетенция, семантический слой, поэтическая функция.*

Introduction. One of the most complex and relevant issues in modern translation theory is ensuring the complete preservation of intertextual connections between source and target texts. This problem becomes particularly relevant in the translation of literary works, as such texts are often referentially linked to other texts. Quotations, allusions, historical and cultural connotations, religious and mythological layers enrich the poetic-aesthetic structure of the text. The translator must not only identify these connections but also convey them appropriately in the target culture and language. This article illuminates this problem through various theoretical sources, examples, and strategies, revealing the impact of intertextual competence on translation quality. One of the current issues in translation theory today is ensuring the degree of

preservation of intertextual connections between the source text and the target text. Intertextual relations, especially in literary works, include multifaceted semantic elements directly related to historical context, cultural layers, and stylistic possibilities of language. The translator assumes great responsibility in correctly understanding these connections and conveying them through alternative linguistic means.

Research conducted by Verbitskaya and Guseva provides important theoretical foundations regarding the transmission of intertextual elements in translation. The authors propose analyzing intertextual elements in the translation process based on specific categories and separately distinguish their semantic and functional characteristics. They substantiate what strategies can be applied by the translator through precise classification of intertextual units.[1] According to the researchers, when intertextual elements are translated, they should be adequately conveyed not only at the level of words but also at deep cultural and connotative layers. This approach serves to strengthen the translator's intertextual competence and ensures the semantic integrity of the translated text. In this sense, this work serves as a relevant scientific basis for methodological and practical approaches to this topic.

Alice's Adventures in Wonderland by Carroll is one of the vivid examples demonstrating how intertextual connections are formed in a literary text and what aesthetic effect they produce. In this work, numerous intertextual units are formed through classical literary images, folklore, mathematical concepts, and Victorian-era social contexts, which serve to deepen the semantics of the work. The text, with its content and form, invites the reader to communicate with other familiar texts, thereby creating new connotative layers.[2] Correctly identifying these intertextual layers in translation and preserving the cultural connotations associated with them emerges as an important issue. This is because these elements provide not only aesthetic pleasure but also ensure the semantic completeness of the text. The translation of Carroll's work places high demands on the translator's cultural knowledge and intertextual competence in this regard. This work creates an opportunity to analyze what strategies should be applied to prevent the loss of intertextual connections in translation.

In her research analyzing the role of intertextual units in the evolution of poetic language, Kuzmina views intertext as an integral part of the literary process. She interprets intertextual connections not only as specific intertextual relationships but also as an important discursive tool in the formation and development of poetic language. According to Kuzmina, poetic language is inherently intertextual, constantly in dialogue with previously created texts.[3] Therefore, correctly identifying intertextual layers in the translation of a poetic work and adequately expressing them in the appropriate language is necessary for preserving the poetic structure. The study particularly highlights how intertextual units undergo changes in the translation process and their functional roles in the poetic system. The theoretical views put forward by Kuzmina serve as an important scientific basis for ensuring the continuity of intertextual connections in translation.

Chernyaevskaya, studying intertextuality as a text-forming category of secondary text in scientific communication, interprets it as a central concept not only within aesthetic or literary texts but also within scientific discourse. She analyzes the role of intertextual units in forming secondary texts, revealing their connection to the source text and how they serve as a means in scientific discourse.[4] The study emphasizes that intertextual connections in the structure of scientific texts emerge not only through reference or quotation but also as an integral continuation of scientific traditions. This approach strengthens with theoretical basis the necessity of identifying intertextual layers in translation and expressing them contextually

appropriately. Chernyaevskaya's views help to understand more deeply the functional importance of intertextual connections in translation and serve as an important source in developing strategies that ensure the complete transmission of these units.

By intertextual connection, we understand the direct or indirect linking of a text with other texts, its reminiscence of other sources through quotations, irony, allusions, parody, or stylistic comments. These connections not only enrich the content of the text but also activate the reader's cultural-aesthetic perception. From this perspective, the complete preservation of intertextual connections in the translation process is an indicator of quality not only of linguistic but also of cultural transposition. Literary texts often contain phrases from other literary sources, historical events, elements related to religion, mythology, or folklore. For example, the references to other Spanish literary works in the novel *Don Quixote* or the Biblical motifs present in Shakespeare's dramatic works are vivid examples of this situation. The translator must understand these contextual references and express them comprehensibly in the target language. This process requires not only language knowledge but also a deep understanding of the source culture.

In many cases, intertextual elements are manifested not at the semantic level but at cultural and associative layers. If the translator fails to perceive this layer or denies it, semantic disruptions appear in the target text. For example, if we take the phrase Pandora's box, this phrase carries a deep semantic load in the mythological context. Its literal translation distorts the meaning of the original text, as this phrase means "a source of unexpected calamities" in the Uzbek language.

Among the ways to preserve intertextual connections in translation, methods such as transformation, transcreation, and annotated translation are of significant importance. Through transformation, the translator replaces intertextual references with appropriate equivalents while maintaining the general structure of the text. In transcreation, the translator recreates the intertextual content in a new style while preserving the aesthetics of the text. Through annotated translation, the translator expands the reader's scope of understanding by providing explanations for complex or unfamiliar intertextual elements. Among these methods, the most controversial approach is transcreation, in which the translator significantly intervenes in the author's style. This, in some cases, may damage the original aesthetic structure of the source text. However, for the purpose of correctly conveying the meaning to the reader, such an approach may become necessary in some cases. Even if the translator applies such an approach, it must be implemented consistently and justifiably.

In literary translations, the disruption of intertextual connections can extinguish the poetic function of the text, depriving the reader of aesthetic pleasure. This is especially noticeable when cultural elements that do not exist in the translation language are directly transferred. For this reason, the method of compensation is widely used in translation. In this method, if it is impossible to directly translate an intertextual unit, the translator fills its place with another cultural or stylistic element. The issue of preserving intertextual elements in translation also depends on the type of translation. For example, in scientific texts, intertextual connections occur more often in the form of quotations and are presented with specific sources indicated. In such cases, the translator mainly focuses on bibliographic accuracy. In literary texts, however, intertextual elements are often presented in a hidden form, which requires intertextual competence from the translator. In modern translation theories, intertextual competence is evaluated as one of the translator's main professional skills. This competence allows the translator to identify intertextual connections, understand their functional role, and select

adequate means in the new linguistic environment based on them. The components of intertextual competence include understanding cultural context, historical knowledge, stylistic sensitivity, and associative thinking skills.

In translation practice, to fully convey intertextual connections, it is necessary to conduct contextual analysis of texts, deeply study the source language and culture, and take into account the cultural and stylistic level expected by the reader. The quality of translation often requires not only linguistic but also intercultural competence from the translator. Each decision in preserving intertextual connections plays a decisive role in shaping the aesthetic, stylistic, and semantic aspects of the translation. Analyses show that neglecting intertextual connections in the translation process hinders the reader's complete understanding of the author's idea. Inadequate translation of intertextual references or their complete removal disrupts the semiotic structure of the text. This situation reduces the potential of the translated text to serve as a complete means of communication. Therefore, the translator must approach intertextual connections with high attention.

Conclusion: In conclusion, preserving intertextual connections is one of the important criteria for translation quality. This should be considered not only from a linguistic perspective but also as an important aspect of intercultural communication. Through strategies such as transformation, transcreation, and annotated translation, the semantic, cultural, and poetic content of intertextual units can be adequately conveyed to the target language. The translator's level of cultural knowledge, understanding of literary aesthetics, and intertextual competence play a decisive role in the successful implementation of this process. Therefore, developing the skill of identifying intertextual connections and effectively conveying them is one of the urgent tasks for translators.

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